

Studies on lanthanide(III) complexes of 2-(*N*-benzoin)amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thiophene

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Abstract : Condensation of 2-amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thiophene with benzoin yielded a potentially tridentate heterocyclic Schiff base 2-(*N*-benzoin)amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thiophene (HBAT) which formed a series of complexes with lanthanide(III) nitrates having formula [Ln(HBAT)(NO₃)₃] where Ln = La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Yb and Lu. These complexes were characterized through elemental analyses, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, UV-Visible, IR and NMR spectral data. The molar conductance values adequately confirmed the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The spectral studies revealed that the ligand has been bonded to the metal ion in a tridentate fashion through the ester carbonyl, azomethine nitrogen and oxygen of hydroxyl group without deprotonation. X-Ray diffraction study of the ligand and [Pr(HBAT)(NO₃)₃] showed that the ligand possesses a tetragonal crystal lattice and the complex possesses orthorhombic crystal lattice. The thermal decomposition study of [La(HBAT)(NO₃)₃] has also been discussed.

Keywords : 2-Amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thiophene, lanthanide(III) nitrate complexes, X-ray diffraction study, thermal study.

Introduction

Metal chelates of Schiff bases are considered to be among the most important stereochemical models in the main group and transition metal coordination chemistry¹⁻⁴. Among the prodigious number and varieties of transition metal complexes, those derived from salicylaldehyde and its derivatives form the major part mainly because of their synthetic proclivity⁵⁻⁸. However a potential group of Schiff base complexes that have received less attention is those derived from heterocyclic system particularly those containing thiophene ring system⁹. In this investigation, 2-aminothiophene¹⁰ has been made stable through carboxyethyl group substitution at position 3 and fusion with a cyclohexane ring at positions 4 and 5 by Gewald synthesis¹¹. Apart from bringing stability to 2-aminothiophene, this substitution provided further scope for coordination and reactivity. This amino derivative of benzothiophene has been condensed with benzoin to form a potentially tridentate Schiff base viz. 2-(*N*-benzoin)-amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]-

thiophene (HBAT). Although the solution behavior of La^{III} and Ce^{III} with benzoin in acetone and synthesis and characterization of solid complexes of lanthanum(III), praseodymium(III), samarium(III), terbium(III), holmium(III), europium(III), neodymium(III) and dysprosium(III) with benzoin have been studied¹² but there has been so far no reports on the synthesis of solid complexes of lanthanides(III) nitrate with 2-(*N*-benzoin)amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thiophene (HBAT). It was therefore of interest to investigate the solid lanthanide(III) complexes of the title ligand.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. Commercial solvents were distilled and used for synthesis. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur analyses were performed using Vario EL III CHNS analyzer. Molar conductance measurements were carried out using 10⁻³ M solution of the complexes in DMSO at room temperature using a Systronics Conductivity Meter type 304.

Magnetic susceptibility values of the complexes were measured at room temperature with a Gouy type magnetic balance. X-Ray diffraction studies were performed using a Siemens D 5005 model X-ray spectrometer.

The lanthanide(III) nitrates were prepared from the corresponding oxides by dissolving them in dilute nitric acid and the salt formed was crystallized.

Synthesis of the ligand :

The ligand was prepared by the condensation of 2-amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]-thiophene with benzoin in 1 : 1 molar ratio in methanolic solution. A solution of benzoin (0.01 mol) in methanol was added to a solution of amine (0.01 mol) dissolved in methanol. The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4 h. The resulting yellow solution was concentrated to half of its original volume and allowed to crystallize. The crystals formed were collected on a filter, washed with methanol and dried. Yield 75% and m.p. 99 °C.

Synthesis of the complexes :

All the complexes were prepared by the following

general method. Lanthanide nitrate (1 mmol) in ethanol (10 mL) was added to a boiling solution of ligand (1 mmol) in ethanol (20 mL) and refluxed on a water-bath for about 10 h. The pH of the solution was then adjusted to 6.5–7.0 and the refluxing was continued for about 6 h. Solution thus obtained was concentrated to half the initial volume and kept overnight. Solid mass separated was filtered, washed successively with ethanol and ether and dried *in vacuum*.

Results and discussion

Reaction between lanthanide(III) nitrate and HBAT can be symbolised by the following equation :

Attempts to prepare 1 : 2 complex were not successful, presumably due to steric factors. Elemental analyses (Table 1), IR and the molecular weight determination by camphor method indicate that the complexes were in a mononuclear form and possess the general formula $[\text{Ln}(\text{HBAT})(\text{NO}_3)_3]$. They are air stable solids, light coloured and soluble in DMF, DMSO and nitrobenzene.

Table 1. Analytical data of $[\text{Ln}(\text{HBAT})(\text{NO}_3)_3]$

Complex	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
		Metal	C	H	N	S
$[\text{La}(\text{HBAT})(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	72	18.71 (18.67)	40.42 (40.33)	3.34 (3.36)	7.54 (7.52)	4.32 (4.30)
$[\text{Ce}(\text{HBAT})(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	71	18.78 (18.80)	40.21 (40.26)	3.31 (3.35)	7.48 (7.51)	4.21 (4.29)
$[\text{Pr}(\text{HBAT})(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	73	18.79 (18.89)	40.13 (40.22)	3.32 (3.35)	7.43 (7.50)	4.23 (4.29)
$[\text{Nd}(\text{HBAT})(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	71	19.13 (19.25)	39.91 (40.04)	3.33 (3.34)	7.38 (7.47)	4.21 (4.27)
$[\text{Sm}(\text{HBAT})(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	71	19.75 (19.90)	39.51 (39.72)	3.29 (3.31)	7.34 (7.41)	4.18 (4.24)
$[\text{Eu}(\text{HBAT})(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	73	19.81 (20.08)	39.63 (39.59)	3.28 (3.30)	7.31 (7.40)	4.19 (4.23)
$[\text{Gd}(\text{HBAT})(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	72	20.01 (20.62)	39.21 (39.26)	3.19 (3.28)	7.28 (7.35)	4.13 (4.20)
$[\text{Dy}(\text{HBAT})(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	71	20.98 (21.17)	38.91 (39.09)	3.20 (3.26)	7.31 (7.29)	4.21 (4.17)
$[\text{Yb}(\text{HBAT})(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	72	22.12 (22.24)	38.48 (38.56)	3.14 (3.21)	7.14 (7.20)	4.08 (4.11)
$[\text{Lu}(\text{HBAT})(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	71	22.31 (22.44)	38.48 (38.46)	3.15 (3.20)	7.06 (7.18)	4.01 (4.10)

The molar conductance values of the complexes were determined in DMSO, DMF and nitrobenzene (Table 2). The values adequately confirmed the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The magnetic moment of the complexes (Table 2) indicate that they are paramagnetic in nature except La^{III} and Ln^{III} complexes which are diamagnetic. The values obtained are in better agreement with expected values except in case of Sm^{III} and Eu^{III} where slightly higher values are obtained¹³. This is due to low J-J separation which leads to thermal population of higher energy levels.

Table 2. Magnetic studies and molar conductance of [Ln(HBAT)(NO₃)₃]

Complex	Magnetic moment (B. M.)	Molar conductance (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)		
		DMSO	DMF	Nitrobenzene
[La(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	D	5.9	11.9	3.2
[Ce(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	2.41	5.5	12.1	2.5
[Pr(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3.52	5.1	12.3	2.3
[Nd(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3.56	5.7	11.5	2.4
[Sm(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	1.52	6.1	11.6	2.6
[Eu(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3.38	5.8	12.0	2.7
[Gd(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	7.81	5.6	12.1	2.4
[Dy(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	10.49	6.2	11.8	2.5
[Yb(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	4.35	5.4	11.7	2.3
[Lu(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	D	5.6	11.6	2.4

The electronic spectra of the ligand in DMSO exhibited two absorption bands at 266 nm and 312 nm due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition respectively. The electronic spectra of the complexes are dominated by ligand bands with a slight red shift. The slight shift was

attributed to the effects of crystal field upon inter electronic repulsion between the 4*f* electrons. There is a weak band in the spectra of the complexes ~ 735 nm due to weak *f-f* transition.

Infrared spectra :

The important infrared frequencies of the ligand and its complexes along with their tentative assignments are given in Table 3. The broad band between 3406–3296 cm⁻¹ due to hydrogen bonded -OH in the ligand shifted downfield to ~ 3390 cm⁻¹ in the complexes is indicative of the coordination of -OH group without deprotonation. It is also apparent by the observation that the strong band at 1350 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{C-O} in the spectrum of the ligand has shown a slight downward shift in the spectra of the complexes. A medium intensity band at 1589 cm⁻¹ in the ligand due to $\nu_{C=N}$ of azomethine is shifted to lower frequencies ~ 1566 cm⁻¹ upon complexation because of coordination of azomethine nitrogen with lanthanide ion. A strong band at 1674 cm⁻¹ due to the internally hydrogen bonded ester carbonyl group is shifted downward to ~ 1647 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicating coordination of the ester carbonyl to lanthanide ion. This type of coordination by ester group has been already reported¹⁴. The substituted thiophene ring vibrations occurring at 1524, 1422 and 1365 cm⁻¹ did not show any appreciable change in the metal chelates¹⁵. This gives conclusive evidence for non-participation of ring sulphur atom in coordination.

In the spectra of the nitrate complexes there are two additional bands observed ~ 1470 cm⁻¹ and ~ 1255 cm⁻¹. These bands are assigned to the ν_5 and ν_1 modes of the

Table 3. Important IR spectral bands of the HBAT and its lanthanide(III) nitrate complexes

Complex	$\nu(O-H)$	$\nu(C=O)$	$\nu(C=N)$	$\nu_5(NO_3)$	$\nu_1(NO_3)$	$\nu(Ln-N)$	$\nu(Ln-O)$
HBAT	3406	1674	1589	-	-	-	-
[La(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3390	1648	1565	1470	1255	419	350
[Ce(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3391	1649	1566	1471	1254	418	352
[Pr(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3390	1650	1567	1470	1256	418	354
[Nd(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3388	1649	1565	1470	1253	419	355
[Sm(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3389	1648	1565	1472	1254	420	352
[Eu(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3387	1647	1566	1471	1255	419	355
[Gd(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3388	1648	1565	1470	1255	420	353
[Dy(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3387	1649	1567	1472	1254	418	354
[Yb(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3388	1647	1567	1471	1253	418	355
[Lu(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	3387	1648	1565	1470	1254	419	353

nitrate ion respectively. The magnitude of the separation ($\Delta\nu$) between these values has been $> 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Thus it can be concluded that the nitrate ion is coordinated to the lanthanide ion in a bidentate fashion¹⁶.

Far infrared spectra of the metal complexes showed several absorption bands which are not observed in the ligand spectra. The band of medium intensity appearing ~ 420 and $\sim 355 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ln-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Ln-O}}$ modes respectively. Absence of M-S bands give added support to the non-participation of ring sulphur atom in coordination.

The above observations strongly support the coordination of the ligand as neutral tridentate ONO donor sequence.

¹H NMR spectra :

The proton NMR spectrum of the ligand displays signals at 6.09, 6.06, 7.20–8.01, 3.4, 2.4–2.6 and 1.3–1.8 ppm assignable to -OH, -CH, aromatic protons, protons of cyclohexane ring, -CH₂ and -CH₃ protons respectively. The observed downfield shifts of the -OH and -CH signals to 6.01 and 5.98 ppm in the spectra of the lanthanum complex are indicative of involvement in coordination of hydroxylic oxygen. The interaction between the -OH and the lanthanide(III) ion does not increase the acidity sufficiently for ionization of the proton. Hence oxygen atom of the -OH group is coordinated to the metal ion without deprotonation¹⁷. Furthermore, the presence of a small downfield shift in the aromatic proton signals confirms the bonding formation. Hence the NMR spectral data further substantiate the mode of coordination suggested by infrared spectral studies.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

The ligand and the complex [La(HBAT)(NO₃)₃] were

subjected to thermogravimetric analysis (Table 4). The ligand undergoes a single stage decomposition in the temperature range 150–320 °C with a DTG peak at 236 °C (Fig. 1). However [La(HBAT)(NO₃)₃] exhibited a two stage decomposition (Fig. 2). The initial stage decomposition started at 150 °C and ended at 210 °C, with a mass loss of the benzoin moiety. The DTG curve shows a peak at 194 °C. The second stage of decomposition occurred in the temperature range 260–590 °C, with a DTG peak at 460 °C. The mass loss agrees well with loss of anion and the formation of La₂O₃ which is stable beyond 590 °C and also the mass of the residue agrees with the mass of the residue obtained in independent pyrolysis.

Fig. 1. Thermal decomposition curves of HBAT

Table 4. Thermal decomposition data of HBAT and [La(HBAT)(NO₃)₃]

Compd.	Decomposition stage	Temperature range (°C)	Peak temperature (°C)	Mass loss (%)	Calcd. mass loss (%)	Probable assignment
HBAT	I	150–320	236	100	100	Decomposition/oxidation of the compound completely
[La(HBAT)(NO ₃) ₃]	I	150–210	194	29.54	29.5	Loss of benzoin moiety
	II	260–590	520	49.63	49.52	Loss of benzothiophene moiety, anion and formation of La ₂ O ₃

Fig. 2. Thermal decomposition curves of [La(HBAT)(NO₃)₃].

X-Ray diffraction studies :

The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of HBAT and its praseodymium complex were taken and indexed to examine the crystallinity of the ligand and complex. The results have been presented in Tables 5 and 6. The diffractogram of HBAT recorded 25 reflections between 2θ ranging from 11 to 36° with maxima at $2\theta = 11.2300^\circ$, which corresponds to interplanar distance $d = 7.8725 \text{ \AA}$. The main peaks have been indexed for tetragonal system^{18,19}. But the diffractogram of [Pr(HBAT)(NO₃)₃] recorded 18 reflections between 2θ ranging from 12 to 66° with maxima at $2\theta = 25.5100^\circ$ which corresponds to interplanar distance $d = 3.4888 \text{ \AA}$. The main peaks have been indexed for orthorhombic system. The crystal system is changed during complex formation from tetragonal to orthorhombic system. The $\sin^2\theta$ and d values obtained have been compared with the calculated values.

Table 5. XRD data of HBAT

d observed (\AA)	Intensity (%)	2θ observed	θ observed	$\sin^2\theta$ observed	$\sin^2\theta$ calculated	hkl	d Calcd (\AA)
7.8725	100	11.2300	5.6150	0.0095	0.0096	200	7.8612
7.1122	19.8	12.4350	6.2175	0.0117	0.0120	210	7.0342
6.1302	2.16	14.4369	7.2184	0.0157	0.0160	211	6.0889
5.8339	0.67	15.1744	7.5872	0.0174	0.0184	102	5.6803
5.4790	1.69	16.1634	2.0817	0.0197	0.0208	112	5.3415
4.9495	21.76	17.9061	8.9530	0.0242	0.0256	202	4.8140
4.6353	3.79	19.1309	9.5654	0.0275	0.0280	212	4.6040
4.2909	0.65	20.6829	10.3414	0.0322	0.0312	320	4.3615
4.1455	4.76	21.4167	10.7083	0.0345	0.0352	321	4.1058
3.8783	77.23	22.9113	11.4556	0.0394	0.0400	312	3.8512
3.7486	2.98	23.7153	11.8576	0.0421	0.0424	401	3.7408
3.5443	3.78	25.1040	12.5520	0.0472	0.0472	322	3.5462
3.4570	1.71	25.7490	12.8745	0.0496	0.0480	420	3.5171
3.3590	4.77	26.5137	13.2568	0.0525	0.0520	421	3.3782
3.3009	12.28	26.9890	13.4945	0.0544	0.0544	402	3.3029
3.1275	3.60	28.5158	14.2579	0.0606	0.0600	313	3.1451
3.0843	3.21	28.9239	14.4619	0.0623	0.0624	510	3.0847
2.9779	13.18	29.9817	14.9908	0.0668	0.0664	511	2.9901
2.8585	10.68	31.2651	15.6325	0.0725	0.0736	521	2.8401
2.7508	2.78	32.5228	16.2614	0.0784	0.0784	512	2.7508
2.7094	1.65	33.0328	16.5164	0.0807	0.0792	333	2.7372
2.6643	1.59	33.6089	16.8044	0.0835	0.0840	423	2.6578
2.6325	1.71	34.0273	17.0136	0.0855	0.0856	522	2.6333
2.5717	3.48	34.8576	17.4258	0.0897	0.0904	601	2.5623
2.5261	1.26	35.5065	17.7532	0.0929	0.0928	611	2.5287

Table 6. XRD data of [Pr(HBAT)(NO₃)₃]

<i>d</i> observed (Å)	Intensity (%)	2θ observed	θ observed	sin ² θ observed	sin ² θ calculated	<i>hkl</i>	<i>d</i> Calcd. (Å)
7.2138	50.33	12.2592	6.1296	0.0113	0.0123	001	6.9454
5.2546	17.23	16.8586	8.4293	0.0214	0.0225	020	5.1346
4.9601	10.05	17.8676	8.9338	0.0240	0.0248	120	4.8932
4.6775	42.17	18.9568	9.4784	0.0270	0.0267	310	4.6877
4.2812	63.69	20.7303	10.3651	0.0323	0.0320	301	4.3076
4.1690	78.46	21.2942	10.6471	0.0341	0.0348	021	4.1297
3.8329	91.30	23.1864	11.5932	0.0403	0.0390	311	3.9017
3.7464	44.11	23.7297	11.8648	0.0422	0.0432	410	3.7064
3.6659	29.06	24.2587	12.1293	0.0441	0.0442	320	3.6641
3.4888	100.00	25.5100	12.7550	0.0487	0.0492	002	3.4725
3.3760	17.99	26.3779	13.1889	0.0520	0.0515	102	3.3975
3.1799	16.95	28.0360	14.0180	0.0586	0.0600	230	3.1449
2.9213	17.87	30.5762	15.2881	0.0694	0.0703	302	2.9053
2.8350	18.30	31.5308	15.7654	0.0737	0.0731	022	2.8494
2.2038	6.22	40.9150	20.4575	0.1221	0.1201	203	2.2222
2.0884	8.40	43.2860	21.6430	0.1360	0.1331	023	2.1112
1.7849	60.46	51.1307	25.5653	0.1861	0.1826	333	1.8024
1.4273	11.61	65.3228	32.6614	0.2911	0.2964	244	1.4147

Fig. 3. Structure of HBAT.

A comparison of these values revealed good agreement between calculated and observed values.

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Fig. 4. Structure of [Ln(HBAT)(NO₃)₃].

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